

RISER: The First All-European RISC-V Cloud Server Infrastructure

by Manolis Marazakis and Stelios Louloudakis (ICS-FORTH)

The European cloud market is estimated to grow from EUR 32 billion to EUR 127 billion from 2020 to 2026, playing a key role in the European economic growth and social development. RISER will develop the first all-European RISC-V cloud server infrastructure, significantly enhancing Europe's strategic autonomy in open-source technologies.

Cloud technologies with an important growth and economic impact include multi-core accelerators and high-speed communication infrastructures, with an expected Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 24.7% from 2022 to 2027 [1]. Cloud infrastructures are expected to serve more than 50 billion users by 2025. Europe clearly needs an advanced energy-efficient EU-based cloud solution driven by EU technology and infrastructures. Thus, the development and long-term evolution of general-purpose and accelerator processors, together with their associated set of hardware and systems software support components, has been widely recognised as a crucial element of open strategic autonomy for Europe [2]. Expanding and validating open hardware interfaces, coupled with making available a fully featured operating system environment and runtime system, enables a pathway of innovation in several domains, including cloud services, which are so widely adopted that they have become an essential part of

everyday life. All of the aspects described above, led to the conceptualisation of the RISER project [L1].

RISER will develop the first all-European RISC-V cloud server infrastructure, significantly enhancing Europe's strategic autonomy in open-source technologies.

RISER will leverage and validate open hardware high-speed interfaces combined with a fully featured operating system environment and runtime system, enabling the integration of low-power components, including RISC-V processor chips from the EPI [L2] and EUPILLOT [L3] projects, in a novel energy-efficient cloud architecture. RISER brings together seven partners from industry and academia to jointly develop and

Figure 1: RISER Architecture logical layers.

Figure 2: System software for the two RISER platforms: accelerator interacting with host, and microserver with cloud software stack

validate open-source designs for standardised form-factor system platforms, suitable for supporting cloud services. Specifically, RISER will build two cloud-focused platforms:

1. An accelerator platform, which includes the Arm RHEA SoC from EPI and a PCIe acceleration board to be developed within the project, which will integrate up to four RISC-V based chips from EUPILOT.
2. A microserver platform, interconnecting up to ten microserver boards all developed by the project, each one supporting up to four RISC-V chips coupled with high-speed storage and networking. Embracing hyperconvergence, our microserver architecture allows for distributed storage and memory to be used by any processor in the system with low overhead. The open-source system board designs of RISER will be accompanied by open-source low-level firmware and systems software, and a representative Linux-based software stack to support cloud services, facilitating uptake and enhancing the commercialisation path of project results.

Three use cases will be developed to evaluate and demonstrate the capabilities of RISER platforms:

- a) Acceleration of compute workloads
- b) Networked object and key-value storage
- c) Containerised execution as part of a provider-managed IaaS environment.

RISER has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101092993. The project is funded under the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) call on "Digital and emerging technologies for competitiveness and fit for the green deal" [L4].

Links:

[L1] <https://www.riser-project.eu>

[L2] <https://www.european-processor-initiative.eu>

[L3] <https://eupilot.eu>

[L4] https://bit.ly/HaDEA_call_digital-Green-Deal

References:

- [1] Data Center Accelerator Market by Processor Type (CPU, GPU, FPGA, ASIC), Type (HPC Data Center, Cloud Data Center), Application (Deep Learning Training, Public Cloud Interface, Enterprise Interface) and Region - Global Forecast to 2027 (Report by GlobeNewsWire Inc, November 2022). <https://bit.ly/401obA5>
- [2] EU strategic autonomy 2013-2023: From concept to capacity (European Parliament briefing, July 2022). <https://bit.ly/43w3hME>

Please contact:

Manolis Marazakis, ICS-FORTH, Greece
maraz@ics.forth.gr

Stelios Louloudakis, ICS-FORTH, Greece
slouloudak@ics.forth.gr

Open and Shared Infrastructure for Software Research

by Jurgen Vinju (CWI and TU Eindhoven)

Research software engineers, scientific programmers, PhD students and postdocs alike spend their time and energy on engineering the software for their research infrastructure. Sometimes this can be reused in follow-up research projects, but most often valuable software output falls like trees in the forest, without an audience, and without users. Surprisingly, even in the academic field of software engineering, research software infrastructure is not sustained, leaving a wide gap of opportunity for more reuse and more impact.

Software has penetrated every aspect of society to the point where it has become critical to its day-to-day functioning. We must learn to better understand software: how to construct it, maintain it, check it and control it. Based on an increased understanding we can learn to better control the risk factors of software (from financial risk to personal safety risk) and we can learn to innovate with higher quality and more agility.

Understanding the complexity of software requires excellent observational instruments that enable top-quality empirical research methods. Since 2009 the Rascal metaprogramming language [L1] has become an infrastructure for empirical research in software engineering. By providing both language-agnostic and language-specific intermediate data representations of source code and data around software processes (versions, issues, discussion), new research was enabled that covers programming languages such as Lua, PHP, Java, C and C++ in a familiar and consistent environment. The development of Rascal and its core supporting language front-ends was done in the context of both national European collaborations such as FP7 OSSMETER and H2020 CROSSMINER and NWO MERITS.

However, there is ample room for growth and improvement. The field is still hampered by a lack of up-to-date, easy-to-use, and easy-to-combine (integrated) instruments for collecting data about software and the software development process. The existing instruments that do exist are scattered, isolated and incompatible. Therefore, we are extending the Rascal platform (and community) for software analysis and transformation with many new necessary high-quality data sources and accurate instruments for software data acquisition and analysis. By design, these instruments will be easy to integrate in order to link data about software in new and unforeseen ways. For example, this year the Ada-air front-end was added to enable the analysis of high-tech components programmed in the Ada language.

On the one hand, all these instruments are comparable to radio telescopes: they acquire the raw data which are essential for knowledge discovery. On the other hand, dissecting software is more like microbiology: every little piece has a different shape and size and requires specialised instruments. Even